

ΣIDERWIN project : how the electrification of primary steel production, as a deep decarbonisation opportunity, could play an important role in the European power system in the future ?

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Abstract

The growing steel industry represents 4% of the total European carbon emissions (EU27). The current coal based blast furnace process used to make primary steel has been widely optimized over the past decades to become as efficient as possible. Because of limited opportunities for further enhancements in the existing process, the decarbonisation of the primary steel industry requires a breakthrough innovative technology.

At the same time, Europe aims to be climate neutral by 2050 and have net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal and the global climate commitment of the Paris Agreement. This means that all sectors of the economy will have to be climate neutral from the power sector to the industry, mobility, buildings, agriculture and forestry. The power sector is at the forefront of the reduction of carbon emissions with the phase-out of carbon-intensive coal production and the development of renewables alongside existing carbon-free generation such as hydropower, biomass and nuclear. This gives the opportunity for the industrial processes to switch to carbon-free electricity and reduce their carbon footprint.

To reach this goal, the European H2020 – ΣIDERWIN project aims to develop a breakthrough process for the primary steel production, based on electrolysis, as a low carbon alternative to the current blast furnace.

Because it is a flexible and electricity intensive technology, ΣIDERWIN's industrial development in Europe is expected to play a significant role in the European power system in terms of electricity demand, and demand-side response capacity.

This paper focuses on the ΣIDERWIN technology and its contribution to the future European power system. Based on projections of the steel demand in 2050 and the specific consumption of this technology, prospective scenarios are simulated in order to assess ΣIDERWIN's contribution in production and demand balancing, and the benefits to the power system. Methodology for this study is presented and discussed.

Introduction

Europe aims to be climate neutral by 2050 and have net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal and the global climate commitment of the Paris Agreement. This means that all sectors of the economy will have to be climate neutral from the power sector to the industry, mobility, buildings, agriculture and forestry. The power sector is at the forefront of the reduction of carbon emissions with the phase-out of carbon-intensive coal production and the development of solar and wind renewables alongside existing carbon-free generation such as hydropower, biomass and nuclear. This gives the opportunity for the industrial processes to switch to carbon-free electricity and reduce their carbon footprint. In this context, innovation is more than ever a necessity to find deep decarbonizing solutions especially for carbon intensive industries, still largely dependent on fossil energy, such as the steel, cement and chemical industries.

For steel industry in Europe, two technologies are used today: the primary steel production based on blast furnaces represents nearly 60% of the European steel production, and the secondary steel production based on electric furnaces covers the remaining 40% [1]. In the present-day blast furnaces, coke is used at a high temperature level to reduce the iron ore. This process has been widely optimized over the past decades to achieve an optimum in terms of coal consumption, and therefore has reduced as much as possible its carbon footprint. However, the steel production still represent 4% of the European carbon emissions (EU27).

To lower carbon emissions of steel production, the European H2020 – ΣIDERWIN project [2], led by ArcelorMittal, aims to develop, build and test a breakthrough electric alternative process for the primary steel production, by implementing electrolysis supplied with low carbon electricity. This technology transforms iron oxides from grinded ores or by-products from other metal industries into iron plates.

Contrary to blast furnace based on coal, the ΣIDERWIN process generates iron with low direct carbon emissions. Furthermore, taking into account the EU objective aiming to decarbonize the electricity production thanks to an important development of renewables in Europe, the indirect emissions of the electricity based ΣIDERWIN technology will also be more and more limited in the future.

Compared to traditional steelmaking plants, the industrial development of this innovative technology could have several advantages such as:

- A reduction by more than 80% of the direct carbon emissions because of coal substitution with electricity,
- A reduction by nearly 30% of the direct energy use thanks to a more efficient process,
- The ability to produce steel from by-products rich in iron oxides from non-ferrous metallurgy residues (for example the bauxite residues from the aluminium industry),
- A fuller decarbonisation of the power mix thanks to the important flexibility potential of the process

As a European leader of the energy sector fully invested in energy transition, and as a partner in the ΣIDERWIN project, EDF is in charge of a parametric assessment to evaluate the integration of potential ΣIDERWIN plants in the future 2050 European power system, with the objective to define the role that could play this flexible and electricity intensive technology in grid balancing and carbon emissions reduction.

The aim of this article is to present the methodology developed to analyse the impact and the interest of a potential ΣIDERWIN industrial development, in terms of energy consumption, costs and benefits for the power system, flexibility potential and carbon emissions reduction.

First, the ΣIDERWIN technology and its energy specifications are briefly described. Then, the methodology, input data and main hypothesis used to build a scenario 2050, are presented. Last, future work and next steps are mentioned.

ΣIDERWIN technology

Overview of the process

The ΣIDERWIN process is based on electrolysis to produce first iron plates which are then converted into liquid steel in electric furnaces.

The different steps of the process are presented in the following picture:

Figure 1. ΣIDERWIN processing route

1. The iron ore is grinded in stirred mills to produce ultra-fine ore.
2. The ultra-fine ore is mixed with caustic soda and water to produce an electrolyte rich in iron oxide.
3. The electrolyte circulates in electrolyzers in which the electrochemical decomposition of the iron oxide takes place, resulting in iron deposit on the cathode and thus producing iron metal plates and oxygen as a by-product.
4. The iron metal plates are washed and extracted from the electrolyzers and then melted in an electric furnace with scrap to produce liquid steel at the end.

Figure 2. Electrochemical decomposition of iron oxide

Energy consumption

In terms of electricity consumption, the first study results are:

- Grinding: 66 kWh/t of iron (2%)
- Leaching: 325 kWh/t of iron (9%)
- Electrolysis: 2720 kWh/t of iron (75%)
- Fusion: 500 kWh/t of iron (14%)
- Overall : 3611 kWh/t of iron

Demand Side Response profile

Industrial processes based on electrolysis are flexible and can easily start and stop or modulate alongside the electricity consumption, and therefore contribute to grid balancing. It is already a reality for example for the aluminium, zinc and chemical sectors. ΣIDERWIN, as an electrolysis technology, could also play a role in the future Demand Side Response (DSR) market.

In order to evaluate the ΣIDERWIN DSR potential in the future European power system, the theoretical DSR profile has been defined on the basis of ΣIDERWIN specifications and industrial feedbacks. The theoretical DSR profile has been validated afterwards in laboratory conditions thanks to the contribution of the University of Aveiro (Portugal), another partner of the project, who has studied the impact of interruptions and modulation on the iron produced.

Figure 3. Example of a DSR profile representation

The ΣIDERWIN DSR profile considered in the parametric assessment is:

- Energy consumption: 2720 kWh/t iron (electrolysis item) so 2693 kWh/t steel
- Available power (P): 92% of the electrolysis power (not 100% because of process constraints on some auxiliaries)
- Notice period (NP): reactive model (without notice period for modelling)
- Activation/deactivation period (AP/DP): reactive model (without AP/DP period for modelling)
- Duration (D): no limit (minimum thermal inertia issues because of a low temperature process <120°C)
- Frequency: no limit (no impact on the iron product)
- Calendar: no limit (not a seasonal process)

ΣIDERWIN industrial development and integration in the future European power system

Methodology

A deep decarbonisation strategy applied to the European primary steel industry, and based on the industrial development of ΣIDERWIN process, an electricity intensive and flexible technology, can have a significant impact on the European electricity system. We wish to analyse the impact and the interest of a potential ΣIDERWIN industrial development for the European electricity system, in terms of energy consumption, costs and benefits for the power system, flexibility potential and carbon emissions reduction at a time horizon of 2050.

This study requires a detailed modeling of the future European power system to assess the difference in dispatching as well as costs between two scenarios, with and without ΣIDERWIN in the power system, and on a European-wide scale. To do so, we use a state-of-the-art unit commitment model, developed by EDF and called Continental, which optimizes and simulates the power system over a set of 20 interconnected countries. It was used for public studies and in particular for recent European projects. For example, it has been used to perform an extensive publicly available study on integrating 60% renewables into the European power system [3], or more recently in EU-SysFlex European project (Pan-European System with an efficient coordinated use of Flexibilities for the integration of a large share of RES) [4].

Continental requires a large volume of input data including the power generation mix of each country through a detailed description of the generating facilities (installed capacity and technical and economic characteristics of each generation unit as well as unplanned outages scenarios), and the hourly load factors of fossil generation, as well as hourly load curve by country. The countries are then linked by interconnection capacities which must be consistent with the European grid operators' development projects. Because weather data is playing a foremost role for generation of renewables (i.e. hydro, wind and solar) as well as in the profile and level of demand, meteorological uncertainty is taken into account through a large number of climate scenarios. This is particularly important at future horizons to have a good dimensioning of the system and in particular the peak demand, sensitive to climate variations, which has a major impact on the benefits that ΣIDERWIN could provide.

Based on this data, Continental optimizes the generation fleet's schedule and produces a detailed hourly description of the power system by country: generation and participation in system services of each power plant, marginal cost and average cost of the system, number of hours of failure, flows at interconnections, CO₂ emissions, etc.

Continental can also iteratively define the economically optimal generation fleet. This optimization is generally only used for the thermal fleet. The following figure maps how Continental works.

Figure 4. Continental methodology

Scenario 2050 – Input data

In order to evaluate the potential contribution of a primary steel industry, based on ΣIDERWIN technology, in the future European power system, it is necessary to first define the future power system and the future steel industry on the European scale in 2050.

Two kinds of input data and hypotheses are needed:

- A scenario for the power system: installed capacities, climate data, electricity demand, grid interconnections, CO₂ price, carbon intensity of power generation and fuel costs.
- Data for the steel industry: growth rate of the European primary steel industry, location of the future plants, electricity consumption of a ΣIDERWIN plant and its DSR profile.

These different input data are presented more in more detail in the two following parts.

Scenarios for the power system

We build a scenario based on the European Union reference scenario for 2050, in its 2016 version (latest version available at the start of the study) [5], as a starting point.

This scenario is a projection up to 2050 of the European energy system, based on all EU policies and directives adopted before December 2014. It has been developed by a modelling consortium led by the National Technical University of Athens, based on the PRIMES model, using assumptions provided by experts from different countries. It serves as a reference point for assessing new public policy proposals.

The European Union reference scenario provides, from 2015 onwards in 5-year increments until 2050, the production and installed capacity by sector (nuclear, wind, solar, etc.) as well as net import by country. We need to cross these annual data with other public data sources in order to build an hourly data set that can be used by Continental to simulate the power system. The detailed method is presented in EU-SysFlex project. [4].

The sources used to complete the data of the EU reference scenario are mainly the public EU database SETIS for wind and solar hourly profiles [6], "Big & Market" scenario from e-Highway for interconnection flow [7], RTE Long Term Adequacy Forecast 2017 for electric vehicle profile generating fleet [8], ENTSO-E Ten Years Network Development Plan (TYNDP) scenarios [9] for the technical-economic characteristics of the thermal groups (allowing in particular to calculate the variable production costs). The assumptions for fixed production costs (capital costs and O&M costs) are based on the International Energy Agency's World Energy Outlook (WEO) 2018 scenario [10]. Carbon intensity and technical features for thermal power plants are consistent with EU-EUCO30 scenarios [11].

The scope of the study covers twenty interconnected countries in Western Europe: Austria, Belgium, The Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. Two of these countries are not included in the scope of the EU reference scenario: Switzerland and Norway, for which we use data from the "Sustainable transition" scenario of the ENTSO-E TYNDP [9].

From these data, Continental model allows us to reconstruct a coherent dataset guaranteeing the supply-demand balance in each country. The installed capacity of gas-fired generation units Open Cycle Gas Turbine (OCGT) and Combined Cycle Gas Turbine (OCCG) in each country is automatically optimized by Continental on the basis of economic criteria.

This dataset has the following main features:

- A high rate of renewable Energy (66% of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in Europe, relative to net demand, with variable renewable energy (solar and wind) representing 35% of net demand.
- 25% of the generation is from thermal plants, 20% of which are gas powered.
- 17% of nuclear generation which is carbon-free.
- A high penetration rate of electric vehicles: almost 50% of the whole estimated vehicle fleet.
- A CO₂ price set at 90€ per ton. This price is currently around 25€/ton but is growing strongly and is set to increase very significantly. The hypothesis is consistent with the current vision of the European Union, but well below the carbon's tutelary value, estimated at around 775€/ in 2050. This hypothesis, which is structuring when it comes to costs and economic analysis of the power system will most likely conduct to sensitivity studies later on. It should be noted that it is difficult to predict.
- A high level of interconnection, anticipating major line developments to allow in particular the integration of variable renewable energy sources.

At this stage of the study, the only storage taken into account in the simulation are pumping stations, which represent significant storage capacities at the European level. No stationary batteries are modelled at this stage. Demand Side Management is not optimized dynamically by the model but the shape of the demand curve takes into account demand side management implicitly for water heaters and 60% of the electric vehicle fleet. A more complete integration of the different forms of storage and Demand Side Management is planned in a later stage of the study.

Steel industry related data

In the first assessment, to model a development scenario for the steel industry in 2050, we consider no relocation and reorganization of the European steel industry (conservative hypothesis in terms of market organization and employment), that is to say the European steel-producing countries will remain the same in the future in comparison with today. A map of the current European steel industry is given by the international and European steel industry associations [12].

The European steel production is expected to grow in the future because of an increasing demand in some steel intensive markets such as the construction and automotive sectors. The average growth rate considered in the study is 0.8% per year [13].

In order to observe the impact of a total decarbonisation of the steel industry, according to the carbon neutral European policy, a total substitution of the blast furnaces with Σ IDERWIN technology is considered in the scenario 2050. Consequently, the coal demand of the European primary steel industry must be replaced by an electricity demand depending on the Σ IDERWIN electricity consumption. This hypothesis, combined with the steel industry projections, enable to define the electricity demand of the European primary steel industry in 2050.

Table 1. Primary steel production per European country and projected electricity consumption

European steel producing countries	Primary steel production 2050 (Mt)	SIDERWIN electricity consumption (GWh)	Electrolysis electricity consumption (GWh)	Electrolysis power (MW)
Austria	9,2	32 783	24 769	2 976
Belgium	6,6	23 665	17 880	2 149
Bulgaria	0,0	0	0	0
Croatia	0,0	0	0	0
Czech Republic	6,4	22 813	17 237	2 071
Finland	3,0	10 550	7 971	958
France	13,2	46 911	35 444	4 259

Germany	39,4	140 490	106 148	12 755
Greece	0,0	0	0	0
Hungary	1,7	6 202	4 686	563
Italy	9,3	33 115	25 020	3 007
Latvia	0,0	0	0	0
Luxembourg	0,0	0	0	0
Netherlands	8,9	31 742	23 983	2 882
Poland	6,3	22 519	17 015	2 045
Portugal	0,0	0	0	0
Romania	2,5	8 908	6 731	809
Slovak Republic	5,6	19 997	15 109	1 816
Slovenia	0,0	0	0	0
Spain	5,5	19 775	14 941	1 795
Sweden	4,0	14 408	10 886	1 308
United Kingdom	10,4	37 139	28 061	3 372
Total EU	132,2	471 018	355 880	42 764

In the study, those projected electricity consumptions per each European steel-producing country are taken into account as an additional electricity demand compare to the EU Reference Scenario [5], and the electrolysis power calculated is used to model an additional and distributed flexibility potential for the power system, limited by the grid connections capacities.

Adapting the power system model to meet additional ΣIDERWIN demand

The initial dataset defining the European power system, in line with EU Reference Scenario 2016 to 2050, is then adapted to take into account the additional demand linked to the industrial development of ΣIDERWIN. Assuming the hypothesis of a 0.8%/year growth in the steel production in Europe, the conversion of the steel industry to ΣIDERWIN process yields an additional demand estimated at 471 TWh per year in 2050 for Europe (54GW) so 12% of the total electricity consumption estimated for 2050 within the scope of the study, with strong variations depending on the country as shown in table 1.

To meet this new demand, and according to the EU environmental policy, it is first necessary to cover the additional generation with carbon-free generation sources. Then, the deployment potential is limited by technical, environmental or political constraints (nuclear phase-out for example) for each country and needs to be taken into account. Finally, we consider that there is no additional potential to develop hydropower and biomass in Europe, and that the development of co-generation will not depend on electricity needs.

Therefore, we increase the generation of the following carbon-free technologies: wind, solar and nuclear, in countries where they are already present.

As shown in the next table, the part of the ΣIDERWIN demand in each steel producing country's electricity demand varies vastly between countries from 0% to +48%. And if we consider that each steel producing country has to cover its own additional electricity demand, it means that the carbon-free share of electricity will need to be increased independently in each country to meet this additional demand. For example, in Austria, the carbon-free generation mix that can be scaled up represents 23% of the country's total generation and the additional steel demand represents 37% of the total demand. Therefore, it would be necessary to increase the carbon free generation by 165%. This option does not seem realistic. As a consequence, we choose to rely on the high volume of interconnections to match the additional demand allowing us to use the European RES potential, with the possibility to adapt the ratio for each generation technology. In particular, given the profile of ΣIDERWIN demand, baseload technologies such as offshore wind and nuclear seem best suited. Several assessment will be carry out in a sensitivity study to represent different technical and political choices and their impact for ΣIDERWIN.

Table 2. Additional demand compared to adaptable generation by country

Country	Siderwin Electric Demand (TWh)	% of Siderwin Demand in Country's Electric Demand	% of carbon-free generation that can be increased (Nucl + Wind + Solar)	% to be applied on Nucl + Wind + Solar
Europe	471	12%	50%	24%
Germany	140	21%	42%	50%
France	47	7%	76%	9%
Great-Britain	37	8%	58%	13%
Italy	33	8%	36%	22%
Austria	33	37%	23%	163%
Nederland	32	21%	29%	71%
Belgium	24	25%	35%	73%
Czech Republic	23	24%	61%	39%
Poland	23	9%	44%	20%
Slovakia	20	48%	64%	75%
Spain	20	6%	71%	8%

For each choice of additional technologies distribution, the installed capacity of onshore wind, offshore wind, solar and nuclear plants is modified. The gas generation is then adjusted automatically by an investment loop that allows to balance supply and demand with at most 3-hour of loss of load.

The electricity price is also an important data, in particular for the techno-economic study of the SIDERWIN technology, which aims to evaluate the steel production cost and the potential loss of revenue due to modulation or interruption. However, because the electricity price is not available for 2050, we need to give an estimate. To do so, several options are available and used in different cases:

- Use the short-term marginal cost. Short-term marginal cost corresponds to the variable cost of the most expensive technology called at each time in the merit order. This cost is the main component of today's electricity price. For a mix adjusted economically, it corresponds in theory to the average production cost. However, in reality, it is straying away because the mix is not optimized economically and it is impossible to know in the long term the price of commodities and externalities (in particular the cost of CO₂ emissions) or the real lifetime of the installations, etc. This is why complementary mechanisms are emerging to compensate for these differences, such as capacity or service system markets. More generally, the design market at this time horizon is likely to undergo major changes: for example a pricing mechanism based on variable costs does not allow the remuneration of zero variable cost RES (see EU-Sysflex study [4] for more details). Moreover, this marginal cost is very dependent on the cost of utilities and the cost of CO₂, which are difficult to predict at this horizon.
- Use of average full cost per MWh. This other indicator has the advantage of being independent of the market design and of guaranteeing coverage of all system costs. However, the assumptions for cost evolution are subject to numerous unknowns (i.e. fixed costs, data relative to hydraulic plants), and these costs do not distinguish base or peak prices. But, even based on incomplete data, it can be used to compare various generation fleets.
- Use of long-run marginal cost. Last, this indicator represents the increase of total production cost due to the insertion of a new use (SIDERWIN), by comparing full cost of generation fleet with and without SIDERWIN consumption. It can be related to an additional consumption to calculate a cost per MWh. This criteria, which has been retained for example by the French transmission system operator (RTE) in its adequacy forecast studies [8] and associated studies [14], seems the most pertinent. Nevertheless, this approach has the drawback of being sensitive to the order in which new uses appear.

In addition to these generation costs, network costs must be estimated on the basis of assumptions about the level of connection voltage. As an example, these costs are currently between 11€/ MWh for voltages of 63,000 to 90,000 volts and 3€ for 400,000 volts. This estimation is in progress.

The next part of the study will focus on the evaluation of the SIDERWIN DSR potential, in particular its electrolyser potential, which represent a meaningful share of the total electricity demand. Given the electrolyser specifications, SIDERWIN should offer a great flexibility capacity, of up to 39 GW, with great responsiveness and without duration or repeatability constraints. SIDERWIN could therefore contribute to the balance of the power system, and in particular replace at least part of the peak needs covered, in the initial scenario, by OCGT plants.

This would mean financial gains, by avoiding the variable costs of thermal generation, but above all the fixed costs of building OCGT plants. This gain will have to be compared to the activation cost estimated by the loss in steel revenue. Moreover, the technical characteristics of SIDERWIN curtailment capacities make it potentially eligible

for the providing of system services (FCR, aFFR, mFRR), which could constitute additional income, albeit on a smaller scale than participating to supply and demand balance. It should be noted, however, that these financial gains will be the subject of a sensitivity study in which ΣIDERWIN technology will be evaluated in competition with other Demand Side Management services at a later stage (e.g. other industrial curtailments and better integration of the Battery Management service for electric vehicles).

In addition to the financial gains for the European power system, and the ability to help RES integration by contributing to grid balancing the curtailment of ΣIDERWIN to replace peaking OCGTs should have a positive impact on the CO₂ emissions of the electrical system, further improving the environmental balance of the steel industry.

Conclusion – Future work

This paper presents a methodology that will be used to assess the impact of the ΣIDERWIN technology on the European power system with vary large share of renewable energies at the 2050 time horizon.

Lowering carbon emissions from heavy industry is a major goal for Europe in order to be carbon-neutral by 2050. In this context, ΣIDERWIN aims to shift steel making process from fossil fuels to carbon-free electricity. At the same time, thanks to the DSR capacities of this technology, it could represent an opportunity to reduce the emissions of the European power system by replacing part of the carbon-intensive peaking plants with a Demand Side Management service. Its curtailment capability should be roughly 40 GW which represents about 10% of the maximum European demand residual to wind and solar generation. This could bring a very large source of flexibility to the European power system.

The total substitution of present blast furnaces with the ΣIDERWIN technology in 2050, requires an adaptation of the electricity generating fleet to meet an additional demand of 470 TWh. This represents 12% of the total European electricity consumption expected by 2050 and is of the same order of magnitude than the consumption of France today. Adapting the European generation mix will require to take into account various constraints: political constraints linked, for example to the phasing out or capping of nuclear power and the acceptability of the development of renewable energies; but also physical constraints linked to the development potential of these renewable energies depending on their location and climate variations (particularly for off-shore wind energy). These constraints may lead to question the relocation of part of the steel plants close to the carbon-free generation or the resizing of interconnection capacities.

The results of this study will be available in October 2020 and transmitted to the European Commission within the framework of the H2020 – ΣIDERWIN project [15].

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